

Università degli Studi di Torino
Scuola di Studi Superiori di Torino "Ferdinando Rossi"

On the modeling of green corridors with Agent-Based simulations

Candidate:
Daniele PROVERBIO

Supervisor:
Prof. Pietro TERNA

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Abstract

Among those strategies that try to safeguard biodiversity by intervening on habitat fragmentation, the so-called “wildlife corridors” are of utmost importance. These green corridors generally consist on infrastructures realized to connect habitats and natural areas; however, as they are often time- and resource-consuming, their traditionally heuristic design has been recently coupled with different mathematical models, which can study and possibly anticipate the corridors perturbative effects on each ecological context.

In the present project, I address such issue by presenting the design and implementation of a computational model which makes use of the Agent-Based paradigm with BDI architecture. In the author’s aims, such combination of modeling characteristics should allow for a close replica of animal behaviors, so that the overall system could be realistically modeled and inquired. Moreover, said approach should prove itself to be flexible and easily manageable even by researchers who are not experts of AI techniques, resulting in a better collaboration among biologists and theoreticians. Finally, a toy model is presented and its preliminary results are analyzed discussed.

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Introduction

Why should we protect the environment? This question is not only philosophically relevant, but it is of great importance when dealing with resources and perception from the general public, particularly when biodiversity¹, landscape and, in general, the relationship between humans and “nature²” are concerned. Usually, when debates on environmental ethics are concerned, there are three main point of views: anthropocentrism, pathocentrism, and biocentrism. If we simplify these positions, we can say that the latest seeks to extend human rights to the whole animal and plant set: according to this vision, it is necessary to protect nature for nature’s sake, to preserve its fundamental rights [5]. Pathocentrism, on the other hand, guarantee human-like rights only to those animals that experience pain (mainly vertebrates) [6]. Hence, according to these two ideas, nature and biodiversity are to be safeguarded because they *must* be, as they possess rights. The anthropocentric paradigm, however, is rather different: it states that everything has to be measured in terms of human well-being [7]. Theoretically speaking, then, an indiscriminate exploitation of environmental resources wouldn’t be completely erroneous, provided that it improves welfare and human rights (to work, to food security, and so on). However, many researches have shown that, on contrary, prudent and respectful management of natural resources is definitely important in modern capitalist economy too. To begin with, the World Health Organization (WHO) showed that many world-wide diseases such as obesity, depression, cancer in various forms, all those emerge after complex interactions among genetics, nutrition and both socio-economical and environmental factors [8]. Second, if human rights apply on future generations too [9], it is compulsory to guarantee that they will have access to natural resources as we have now. It is then necessary to manage non-renewable resources, preserve environmental recovery times and improve their resilience [8]. Finally, keeping ecosystems in dynamical and healthy shape is mandatory to preserve the so-called “ecosystem services” (i.e. breeding ground, living seas, drinkable water, pure air, pollination, prevention from floods, tourist sites and cultural heritage) which are tightly related to economical and social development [10, 11]. A key example: in Europe, it was calculated that the complete loss of ecosystem services would correspond to losing €50 billions per year [12].

Despite being presented with due simplifications, the pragmatic necessity to protect the environment is quite straightforward, no matter one’s ethical ideas. Historically, the most common protection strategy was to demarcate parts of territory that would be consequently maintained untouched and free from human exploitation. The idea of preserving natural areas [13, 14] led to the creation of natural parks, starting from mid XIX century to all XX century: national States concentrated their effort in identifying and create preserved areas, mostly in frail or particularly attractive regions [15–17]. Nowadays, at an international level, the definition and management

¹As in the Convenzione per la Diversità Biologica (www.cbd.int), we define biodiversity as “the variability of all living organisms that are included in aquatic, terrestrial and marine ecosystems and in those ecological complexes to which they belong to. Interactions among living organisms and the environment lead to functional relationships that characterize diverse ecosystems and guarantee their resilience, their well-conserved status and the provision of the so-called ecological services [1, 2].

²It is quite hard and not unambiguous to state when environments are “natural” [3], since human interventions have been shaping the Earth in a deep way that is yet not fully understandable. In fact, the term “Anthropocene” is often introduced so to speak of a new geological era [4]. Nonetheless, we would not go deeper in such debate as it exceed this text purposes.

of National Parks (and regional Parks, natural oasis, etc.) is supported by the International Union for the Conservation of Nature (IUCN, <https://www.iucn.org/>) [18].

Although safeguard strategies such as isolation and protection of closed and limited areas have been mainstream during the past centuries, starting from the '80s many studies have showed that these solutions are rather simplistic and not completely effective when dealing with progressive world-wide habitat loss and biodiversity reduction [19]. In fact, progressive man-made impacts over territories that are located between natural areas causes their isolation, both from a geographical and a functional point of view; as a consequence, it becomes impossible to share resources, populations and genetic material. Since genetic robustness of closed animal or plant populations weaken in time [20, 21], and considering that loss of exchanges between different populations prevent recovery and repopulation, a single natural park lacks of the necessary resilience to ensure its biodiversity's welfare. Moreover, as Parks are usually of national extension, they are not always able to cover the migratory areas of many animal species [22]. Consequently, although maintaining natural parks as cradle and shelter for living beings is essential, experts have repeatedly suggested that it is equally necessary to develop safeguard projects at an international level and via well-planned networks [23].

Green corridors are considered by such strategic planning as key features: in fact, they are infrastructures that are specifically designed and built to de-fragment and connect habitats and populations. Important examples are wildlife passages over roads and channels, humid regions, toad tunnels, channels for migrating fishes, green areas across fields and urban areas; in addition, said corridors are often placed transnationally, and remediation and conservation actions are coordinated among states [24, 25]. Nonetheless, there are two main difficulties for implementing corridors. First, they can be expensive: as they are works of environmental engineering, resources are needed. Second, in order to assess their efficacy and coherence with respect to the starting goals, many years are often needed [23]. Hence, in order to help designing such works, that are to be placed in complex ecological contexts, various mathematical modeling approaches have been being developed and proposed during the last years. By doing so, not only researchers have been progressively being helped by reliable instruments that simulate realistic outputs from given inputs, but they are also able to obtain data in a cheap and quick way, and then propose data-based decision making solutions.

Therefore, the present project's aim is to develop and implement a model with both description and prediction roles, so that it may help field operations made by environmental biologists. To do so, after a brief introduction to green corridors and to state-of-the-art modeling strategies, I am going to present the architecture of said custom model: after that, a complete toy model example (simulation, qualitative and quantitative analysis) will be shown, focusing on how it works and how to manage data and information. Finally, I would like to point out that the present text only represents the first half of a bigger project: the second one, developed by my colleague Roberto Costantino³, will present the model validation and the use of realistic parameters, as well as data generation from real geographical contexts.

³As of today, still being elaborated.

1.1 Thesis synopsis and aims

This thesis is divided into sections that reflect the necessary passages for developing the whole project:

1. **Introduction** to the problem and project overview.
2. **Corridors for conservation**: conservation and ecosystem connection strategies using green corridors are discussed. In addition, I present various studies that analyse usefulness and efficacy of said corridors by means of field studies and measurements.
3. **Mathematical models**: during latest years, effectiveness of green corridors has being evaluated by means of different kinds of mathematical models too; those ones are presented in this section. Moreover, the Agent-Based simulation paradigm is introduced, focusing on the most performing programming architectures.
4. **An Agent-Based toy model**: within this section, I describe the design, implementation and analysis of a simplified model to study the dynamics of a complex system composed by animals and plants. An example of qualitative and quantitative analysis is also shown, and preliminary results are discussed.
5. **Conclusions and remarks**: this last section concludes the present thesis. It summarizes working hypothesis and conclusions and suggests a few ways in which to extend the project as well as to improve the model.
6. **Appendice A**: I discuss the system dynamics from an analytical point of view; in addition, I introduce the role of stochastic fluctuations in the system studies.
7. **Appendice B**: the complete programming code is shown.

Corridors for conservation

Among environmental architecture interventions, green corridors represent state-of-the-art solutions for biodiversity conservation when fragmented territories and habitats are involved. Generally, green corridors are defined, particularly when inserted in a coordinated system of green infrastructures, as a strategically planned network composed by high quality natural and semi-natural areas (namely, those with low human impact) which, in turn, involve different environmental features such as trees, bird shelters, humid areas and so on. Said corridors are usually designed and managed in order to guarantee various ecosystem services and to protect biodiversity in rural and urban frameworks [12]. Firstly developed to support migrating activities of species like birds and ungulates, corridors are nowadays used to stimulate the movement of animal and plant populations between the so-called “biodiversity islands” [23], namely closed and limited areas, that are often separated by infrastructures or human activities, in which numerous species live without having, otherwise, the possibility to move and to mate. However, it is important to point out that green corridors have been developed non only for biodiversity sake, but also to provide services to human communities: on one hand, healthy ecosystems provide services like pollination, water filtering and raw materials [10]; on the other hand, safe passages for animals make them divert from fields and roads, thus reducing dangers for humans too¹ or crop waste.

Fig. 2.1 Artistic representation of a toad tunnel, an artificial corridor running under the road level to help amphibians to cross it, particularly during the mating period. Not only this infrastructure avoids toads death, but it also improves road safety by preventing accidents caused by slippery ground due to mashed animals.

Other than connecting territories, experts identified five functions from green corridors: habitat, filter, barrier, source, sink [23]. “Habitat”: a green corridor can be a temporal habitat for several species, allowing them to settle and to colonize areas in which they had previously got extincted (for instance, plant species may root on a corridor infrastructure, then providing shelter and food to crossing animals). “Filter” and “barrier” actions are similar, since corridors can prevent some or all species to cross; for instance, toad tunnels protect amphibians because, on one hand, they prevent bigger predators to go after them, while, on the other hand, they channel

¹Road accidents are of utmost importance, as in Italy, during 2015, 18 people died and 15.000 animals got involved. The problem is economically relevant, too: it was estimated that in Lombardia alone (a region in northern Italy) more than 300.000 € are spent each year for refunds and damages [26].

the batrachians in fixed routes far from roads. “Source” and “sink” functions are one the opposite of the other: a source-like corridor repopulates a territory with new populations, while a sink-like corridor tries to attract scattered individuals or chemicals. As an example, I cite the function of pollutant attractor and filter that is typical of a green belt in urban areas.

Although I showed only positive examples, I recall that the same functions may lead, in principle, to negative effects on the same biodiversity that one is trying to preserve. For instance, the “sink” function may cause unbalanced predator-prey ratios, thus bringing the populations to collapse; alternatively, the “barrier” function might prevent certain species, that biologists were trying to help migrating, to move through the corridor. Because of these reasons, it is necessary to plan the creation of green corridors with the utmost care, while balancing the known systemic aspects and by trying to speculate about the unknown ones: a fruitful and efficient intervention only comes after a deep comprehension of the available data and of the system dynamics [27, 28].

Fig. 2.2 Potential components of a green infrastructure, a coordinated network of green corridors and other kinds of architectural interventions. Core areas are those that are protected as natural parks (Natura 2000 Forest); then, various kinds of corridors can be found: natural (rivers), restored (reedbed) or artificial ones (wildlife overpass). Moreover, it is necessary to create multi-functional zones where compatible land uses can join forces to create land management combinations that support multiple land uses in the same spatial area. [Adapted from “Building a Green Infrastructure for Europe” by European Commission [12]]

As of today, many green corridors have already been created worldwide and many others are being designed and built [24]. In Canada, a network of wildlife infrastructures for protecting and monitoring wild fauna is perfectly functioning [29]. The WWF and the Nepalese government collaborated to develop the Terai Arc Landscape, a narrow sub-tropical corridor crossing India and Nepal; grasslands, forests and river valleys host rare and endangered species such as the Indian rhino, the Asiatic elephant and the Bengal tiger [30]. A series of bridges and tunnels can be seen in Christmas Island, Australia: they protect the spectacular migrations of red crabs from the outback to the sea [24]. In Europe, one of the biggest infrastructures is the European Green Belt aimed to create the backbone of an ecological network that runs from the Barents to the Black and Adriatic Seas [31]. In Italy, then, an important corridor is expected to connect the Alps with the Mediterranean Sea

through Lombardia and Liguria regions [32], while numerous wildlife bridges can already be seen over roads and highways (e.g. the Mi-To highway [33]). Moreover, many European projects are being developed thanks to dedicated funds from the LIFE (“The Financial Instrument for the Environment”) [22] project, supported by the Nature 2000 UE network [34].

2.1 Efficacy of green corridors

A green corridor can be considered “effective” when it produces the results expected during the designing process, while minimizing costs and collateral effects. As a consequence, it is necessary to carefully evaluate the overall framework and to explicit the conservative aims (being them animals movement, genetic exchange, areas repopulation and so on). Hence, one should choose variables and metrics that could help to quantify the corridor efficacy and to compare it with that of other proposals [35]; this holds for both qualitative field evaluations and quantitative predictions from models. The most used variables, as they are cheap and fast to be measured, are usually the species movement rates and the habitats connectivity degree. Various empirical and theoretical studies have shown that placing corridors into dynamic environments is indeed important to stimulate and improve habitat connectivity to protect biodiversity [36, 37] and to make animal migration easier [38]. However, in general, the overall efficacy may depend on the considered species (for instance, empirical data suggest that corridors are, on average, more effective for terrestrial animals, river fishes and plants than for birds) [39, 40] and on the corridor dimension [41, 42]. In addition, some theoretical works have shown that genetic exchange between previously isolated populations could benefit from the presence of green corridors that improve resilience and maintain a healthy biodiversity [43]. Nonetheless, other studies highlighted how these interventions, on the contrary, could be frail if the complexity of the considered system is not carefully taken into account: in such cases, negative effect could arise, such as diffusion of weed or antagonist species or fires [44].

Designing green corridors is therefore a non-trivial challenge for biologists and environmental architects: even though said infrastructures have proven themselves to be useful and effective in safeguarding biodiversity and providing ecosystem services to human communities, it is always necessary to balance carefully costs and benefits, being them of economic or environmental nature. In addition, one should also consider that a corridor often shape the territory in a non-reversible way. Because of these reasons, in addition to empirical experience coming from decennial field studies, it could be useful to support the current knowledge with instruments of different nature that help to explore a manifold of possibilities in a simplified, yet cheap and efficient way. As it will be elaborated throughout the following section, interest in the field of mathematical models in ecological contexts is increasing, as they represent a powerful tool to understand, reproduce and, hopefully, predict the results of complex interventions in complex frameworks.

Mathematical models

A mathematical model is a complete method for studying systems¹ of interest. The reasons why models are generally useful are manifold: to understand the dynamics of the given system (*understanding*), to predict its evolution (*prediction*), to highlight and explain its inner interactions (*heuristic*). Among the different kinds of mathematical models, computer simulations are of great importance. Designing and exploiting a simulation involves choosing the most suited class of models for the given problem (equation-based, individual-based, hybrid), defining the key species and main variables, abstracting the underlying relationships, implementing the designed framework in a proper form that can be interpreted by computers, calculating the algorithm outputs, visualizing and analyzing obtained data [45]. In addition, using models and simulations is undoubtedly advantageous from a practical point of view, as it helps to explore many possible configurations with low cost in terms of resources and funds involved, allowing researchers and planners to compare and contrast different hypothesis and to speculate about the results with an unprecedented power and flexibility. This particularly holds when environmental architecture and territorial planning are considered, as their interventions are often expensive and irreversible [23]. Thanks to appropriate simulations, on the contrary, it is feasible to obtain preliminary information about realistic outputs coming from tested configurations; moreover, it is also possible to verify the process and thus to get quantitative data on which to ground effective, efficient and finalized plannings.

As mentioned, computer models can be roughly divided into three groups: *equation-based models* (EBM), *individual-based models* (IBM) and hybrid models, that merge characteristics of the previous ones².

Briefly speaking, equation-based models are mostly used starting from deep knowledge of the system mechanics, to describe and forecast in a deterministic way the future states given the initial one. Once stated the equations, thus, simulations solve them through numerical approaches or Monte Carlo chains [46]. However, it is rather difficult to formalize and solve these models when we consider individual scales, or when unknown elements apply, or when they are particularly difficult to be stated in mathematical terms (such as “intelligent” decisions), or even when different stochastic sources are present, that one cannot summarize into Wiener terms [47].

As an alternative, *individual-based models* tackle the problem with a different level of complexity, as they firstly determine the dynamics of a single individual; after that, they group singles into societies that are then embedded in a proper environment (which is then naturally introduced in the model). Hence, during the simulation, the collective dynamics is generated in real time from interactions between singles and the environment. Consequently, it is not possible anymore to predict a deterministic mechanics; on the contrary, complex phenomena and emergence of non-predictable *patterns* are studied phenomenologically, starting from

¹In science, a system is defined as “any object of studies that, even if composed by different elements that are mutually connected and interacting among themselves and with the environment, reacts and evolves as a whole, following its own general laws” (Enciclopedia Treccani).

²For instance, it is possible to obtain a hybrid models by adding diffusive elements, ruled by diffusion equations, to an individual-based model.

simulations themselves; moreover, stochastic elements can be easily added, while individual “rationality” can be dealt with using mainly Game Theory formalization [48].

If we then consider modeling approaches that address green corridors, in the present section a specific IBM approach, that of *Agent-Based* (ABM) modeling, is introduced and discussed, focusing particularly on a design architecture to formalize individual rational elements, called *Belief-Desire-Intention* (BDI); then, the choice of using said architecture in the main model is justified. To end with, with the purpose of providing an overview of the current works, a brief discussion on the ABM models literature is provided, focusing on those that address green corridors and their results.

3.1 Agent-Based Models

An agent is a computational entity such as a software program or a robot that can be viewed as perceiving and acting upon its environment and that is autonomous in that its behavior at least partially depends on its own experience. [G. Weiss, *Multiagent systems: a modern approach to distributed artificial intelligence* [49]]

Agent-based models are generally less “simple” than equation-based ones, as they are able to inquire intelligence, through combination of different learning elements, adaptation, evolution and *fuzzy logic*; in addition, ABMs are characterized by a “bottom-up” approach, that starts from the individual representation of components and behaviors and aims at understanding global features emerging from single interactions. In spite of describing the system state with global variables, it is then possible to model individual entities, called “agents”, assuming that they possess proactive abilities and embedding them in a specific environment (which can be dynamic as well) [50]. Hence, Agent-Based models are based upon three fundamental abstractions: the agent (the autonomous source of activity); the society (a group of interacting agents); the environment (context in which agents act and interact).

According to this approach, ABMs seems to be particularly appropriated when addressing extended ecological systems, as it allows by design to deal with autonomous and proactive entities embedded in an environment; moreover, those entities are spatial and they are given specific behaviors [51, 52]. In addition, from a technical point of view, it is usually simpler to know individual behaviors owned by the studied subjects (e.g. animals) rather than the mechanics underlying their interactions, as required by equation-based approaches. Hence, in ecological contexts, interdisciplinary among modelers and biologists can be greatly stimulated. Afterwards, the holistic vision upon the system may be obtained during the simulation cycles by observing the possible emergence of qualitative and quantitative features.

Finally, it is possible to formalize an ecosystem with a hierarchic set structure (Fig. 3.1), ranging from the individual to the biosphere and by defining, according to the chosen scale, an *agent society* as a temporally indexed structure [53]: $AgSoc = (Pop^t, Org^t, MEnv^t, SEnv^t)$, where *Pop* represents the population structure within the society, which is composed by individuals or sets of individuals, *Org* is the organization structure (set of behavior and interaction), *MEnv* is the set of physical environmental structures available to society and *SEnv* is the set of symbolic environmental structures; everything is related to time t (global index for evolution) [54]. When the present ecological context is considered, *Pop* represents the animal population, *Org* is the set of semantic rules for action, reaction and interaction, *MEnv* is the set of physical structures like food, corridors and so on, *SEnv* is spatiality as a whole (which is in turn differentiated into a certain domain which is e.g. divided in patches, toroidal, etc.).

A “meta-modeling” advantage for spatial ABMs supported by qualitative animations, is their interpretability, which is necessary to stimulate a fruitful interdisciplinary collaboration between modelists, biologists, architects

Fig. 3.1 Schematic representation of a ABM: single individuals (even belonging to different populations), can interact among themselves while receiving environmental feedbacks and information. After that they actively evolve through cooperation or competition in order to modify the system state [48].

and policy makers. Letting the dynamics evolving within the replica of a physical space, coupled with the possibility to implement behaviors that were confirmed by ethological studies, helps to settle a shared basis. This would then help researchers from different fields to discuss without ambiguity.

3.1.1 The Belief-Desire-Intention architecture

A classic paradigm for the inner architecture of an Agent-Based simulation is the BDI (Belief-Desire-Intention) approach, based on the philosophy of actions [55] and of agent/environment interactions [56]. Such approach makes use of the so-called *intentional instance*, according to which we can associate an “inner rationality” to agents, that is appropriately formalized through semantic declarations [57]. However, tackling the long-lasting debate about the definition of “rationality” and “free will” is beyond the scopes of the present text, whose purpose is purely pragmatical. Anyway, as McCarthy writes, the intentional instance is appropriate in the following sense:

To ascribe *beliefs, free will, intentions, consciousness, abilities, or wants* to a machine is legitimate when such an ascription expresses the same information about the machine that it expresses about a person. It is useful when the ascription helps us understand the structure of the machine, its past or future behaviour, or how to repair or improve it. It is perhaps never logically required even for humans, but expressing reasonably briefly what is actually known about the state of the machine in a particular situation may require mental qualities or qualities isomorphic to them. Theories of belief, knowledge and wanting can be constructed for machines in a simpler setting than for humans, and later applied to humans. Ascription of mental qualities is most straightforward for machines of known structure such as thermostats and computer operating systems, but is most useful when applied to entities whose structure is incompletely known. [McCarthy, *Ascribing Mental Qualities to Machines* [58]]

Without going deeper into the debate that is typical of psychological sciences about consciousness and its inner states, what is particularly relevant is that the BDI paradigm treats simulations *as if* the virtual agents were rational, in the sense that they are capable to elaborate proactive strategies to modify their own beliefs and the surrounding environment in order to fulfill their goals. To do so, an agent necessitates of a finite set of possible

actions, normally organized in a proper decision tree, and of commitments that are purpose-oriented [59]. To make it simple by using a popular vocabulary, the agent should have a definite long-term goal (*desire*) and a set of short-term actions³ that it *wants* to execute in order to reach its purpose (*intentions*), given its individual knowledge about the system state (*believes*). Said actions are usually organized into hierarchical structures (for example, the mentioned decision tree) called plans. Naturally, the architecture can be further complicated at will by introducing multiple *desires* (potentially conflicting) and by implementing different plan layers, so that one can even obtain meta-plans (plans about choosing plans) and so on [48, 60].

Fig. 3.2 Schematic representation of an abstract BDI architecture (adapted from [48]).

Despite looking potentially intricate, the process of formalizing a BDI architecture was created and has been improved starting from Cohen and Levesque’s pioneering work in the 90s [61] within the framework of Artificial Intelligence studies; moreover, it has been constantly improved in terms of standards and protocols [59], to the point of being included in numerous libraries from different agent-based programming environments (GAMA included [62]. GAMA is the chosen IDE for agent-based modeling; it makes use of the Gaml language (Java dialect) and is freely available to developers and programmers [63]). Therefore, BDI libraries can be easily accessed and exploited by researchers. In addition to being accessible, the recent IT developments allow to use high-level programming languages and user-friendly syntactical structures, that help researchers to develop simple-to-use models with low computational cost, high performances and good realism. Preliminary experiments showed that the *simple_bdi* GAMA plugin can be easily used by people with fairly low knowledge about programming and Artificial Intelligence [64]. By doing so, accuracy and efficiency of simulations are kept, while the code interpretability and the programming flexibility are improved.

Such coding simplicity and comprehensibility, coupled with the realistic assumption to consider simulated animals (at least, great mammals) as rational ones, led to the idea of developing a BDI Agent-Based model; therefore, it would be possible to handle discrete entities with individual behaviors and rationality that make the agents to proactively act in a given environment. This project novelty, we believe, lies within the combination of “rational” agents with spatial characteristics, embedded in a continuous space-time, and the ease of implementing them even without being particularly advances in the AI field, thus stimulating interdisciplinary collaboration among programmers and biologists.

³An “action” is considered both as a practical activity and as communication, provided that the latter is considered as sharing of performative (non only informative) sentences [48].

3.2 Agent-Based models in literature

During the latest years, thanks to IT improvements, augmented calculation power and the diffusion of the agent-based paradigm, many models have been developed to assist environmental conservation plans. Although they share common simulation methodologies and shared research protocols, said models are also intrinsically different one another in various important ways: for instance, the way they treat space, the way time is handled, environmental characteristics, inner agents architecture, animals movement rules, the way that breeding and learning are considered, species interactions [65] and the chosen measured variables [66–69].

I now propose a brief overview of those literature models that were considered more relevant for the present purposes, the main idea being to discuss how the cited features may be combined according to the research aims.

To begin with, I cite a few examples of those models that are framed over a specific context, often by modeling a focused species within a selected geographical region. After the model design, its purpose is then to support targeted interventions made by biologists and policy makers. There are several models of this kind tailored around big North America mammals such as mooses [70] and grizzly bears [71]. The first one addresses animal crossing of roads in order to reduce accidents with vehicles, while the latter aims at minimizing the green corridors economical costs. A third interesting model considers South America jaguars and subsequent interactions with their habitats, in order to develop a prevention and monitoring tool that would assist an endangered species [72].

Another class of models is represented by more abstract ones, that aspire to achieve universality and reproducibility of results. The main studied arguments are the interactions among animal species and human socio-economical activities [73, 74] and the assessment of resources and intervention managements [75–77]; in the latter case, a few spare examples are given by projects that specifically consider green corridors and their effectiveness. A key example is provided by the paper *Habitat corridors facilitate genetic resilience irrespective of species dispersal abilities or population sizes* [43], in which the author inquires the corridors efficacy in preserving genetic diversity within animal populations; the conclusion is that an improvement of genetic exchange among fragmented populations would result from even a slight increase of the corridors width, thus improving genetic diversity as a result.

As seen, each combination of modeling features gives insight onto different system characteristics by highlighting some while possibly neglecting some others (still possibly relevant). Consequently, many concurrent models proliferate, since they may share a subset of features but may differ in others. In particular, as mentioned above, researchers have developed both “rigid” (tailored for a particular ecological configuration) and “flexible” (abstract models whose parameters should be tuned appropriately in order to be validated and to be applied) models; for this reason, we considered that designing and implementing another model could have been a fruitful activity to propose a novelty element in the general panorama. Said Agent-Based model, that will be further discussed in the following section, is hence intended to address environmental conservation problems, in particular those related to the green corridors management.

An Agent-Based toy-model

Making a complete and realistic model requires different steps that can be summarized as following: 1) getting data, behavioral schemes and real cases; 2) make a mathematical (or computational) model that reproduces the dynamics and the interactions of the system components. While doing so, it is important to choose an appropriate scale, the entities and to define the variables, as well as to implement the model in a language that a computer is able to compile; 3) getting simulated data and analyse them; 4) validate the model by comparing predicted data with real data, hence validating or falsifying the modeling hypothesis and tuning the parameters; then the process restarts from point 1, thus closing the knowledge cycle and improving our system understanding and modeling power. A complete experimental and validation cycle, then, aspire to provide, on one hand, knowledge and system comprehension and, on the other hand, to generate quantitative and qualitative predictions concerning the considered phenomena [78].

Since the whole project is separated in two distinct phases (this one and my colleague Roberto Costantino's own work¹, I will now concentrate on designing a mathematical computational model to address behavioral schemes of a specific class of animals (presently, great vegetarian mammals) embedded in their environment; the modeling process is intended to be as general as possible, so to allow further tailoring over particular species (e.g. elks, deers, chamoises...) by parameter tuning, or further framing in a specific geographical contexts (e.g. a single natural Park). Moreover, different examples of feasible measurements are provided and analysed, stressing the possibility to exploit the model as a flexible and powerful testbed.

By doing so, the present modeling project has the following purposes: to develop a mathematical and computational framework that is coherent and properly functioning, keeping in mind that it is intended to support a further and more detailed implementation of the different scenarios that have been studied by environmental biologists; then, to justify the broader hypothesis, that is, to be actually able to simulate complex ecological dynamics into the general context framed by agents and interactions among them and the environment, thus showing the effectiveness and the usefulness of such *in silico* models. A third purpose is to create a user-friendly interface that other researchers and the public could exploit, perhaps in "gameful" [79] sessions that could help them to get in touch with the problem through "serious games" playing [77]. According to these ideas, the presented model is, in fact, a toy model²: it is not meant to be totally complete, yet it helps to explore a phenomenon, to qualitatively investigate it and to observe how certain parameters influence the outcomes. Finally, it will serve as basis for a more complete and validated work that is being carried out by my colleague R. Costantino.

¹R. Costantino's work is still being developed and concerns mainly the model validation and its application to real frameworks.

²Among mathematical models, toy models are purposefully simple, without too many details, yet useful in order to explain specific aspects of a given system [80, 81].

4.1 Design and implementation

A computational model can hardly comprehend everything. On the contrary, once a phenomenon is studied, one should isolate the main features (the simplest or the most representative ones) without considering too much details that can be neglected as a first approximation. Hence, to begin the modeling process, we defined a large class of animals, we embedded them into an abstract environment and we gave them quite general behaviors; said main abstractions on which the model is grounded are going to be presented in the present chapter. As aforementioned, tuning the parameters and refining the choices will then be performed in a second time, so that it will be possible to tailor the present model to specific species and ecosystems.

4.1.1 Environment

The model first main character is the environment. It is defined as a regular, non-toroid squared domain $Env = \langle x_k; y_k \rangle$ (where $k \in [0; dim]$ and dim represents the edge length). Note that, thanks to GAMA software, it would be possible to upload GIS maps, thus working with precise and real scenarios. Said domain is then divided in squared patches that reproduce two “safe” areas and a dangerous one that separates them, as suggested in [43, 44]. Then a “corridor” is placed to connect safe areas; moreover, different resources are also placed randomly. A representation is shown in Fig. 4.1.

Fig. 4.1 Representation of the simulated environment. Green = safe areas (1); White = dangerous area (2); Yellow = corridor (3); Dark green blocks = resources (4).

The implementation strictly follows the design: environment Env is therefore a limited grid $Env = \{0..dim\} \times \{0..dim\}$ (conventionally, $dim = 100$). In principle, it is also possible to add dynamical evolution of grass or other punctual features; although this has not been implemented in the present model, I suggest the possibility to formally define e.g. grass as $grass[t] : (\{x_k, y_k\} \in Env, t) \mapsto b \in \mathbb{N}$, thus associating a scalar value to each grid cell.

On the other hand, the evolution of resures (that may mimic trees, bushes, pools, shelters and so on) is dynamic. Hence, each resource Res_j is identified by its coordinates $\{x_j, y_j\}$ and by an integer value representing its available quantity $res(t) \in \mathbb{N}$. By tuning said value, it would be possible to choose among different configurations according to the considered scenario.

The dangerous area is then implemented as a rectangular domain $Peril = \langle x_p, y_p \rangle$ whose dimensions are $\{dim_{peril} \times dim\}$. It simply splits into two parts the global domain. $dim_{peril} = 1/5 \cdot dim$ was arbitrarily set as an average value. Further studies about its influence are suggested. The dangerous area represents a generic cause of territorial fragmentation (a road, a channel, a human infrastructure) and it is associated to a non-zero

probability of an agent dying during the crossing: $p_{die} = P[die\{An_i s.t. x_i(t), y_i(t) \in Peril\}](t)$ (where An_i is the i -th animal agent and die is a built-in method such that $N_{tot} \rightarrow N_{tot} - 1 \wedge delete\{An_i\}$, where N_{tot} is the total number of animals). The initial value of p_{die} is at a first instance set equal to 0.01 (it means that, at time t , an animal that is crossing the dangerous area has 1% probability to die accidentally); however, such parameter can be estimated from historical records of accidents involving animals within the studied region and then by performing standard statistical analysis [27, 70].

Finally, the “corridor” represents a shelter zone that crosses the dangerous area while linking the two safe ones. It is peril-free, but also resource-free. In further developments, it would be possible to place dynamic resources as well as “incentives” for the animals to cross, according to the researchers’ aim. Corridor dimensions are $length_{cor} = dim_{peril}$, which is fixed, and $width_{cor}$ (variable parameter).

4.1.2 Animals

The agent Animal is naturally the fundamental computational unit. As mentioned above, the modeled class of animals is that of the great vegetarian mammals; therefore, in order to achieve the desired level of realism, it has been necessary to design and implement them as proactive agents, not simply mechanic. In order to integrate said requirements, while maintaining the model simple enough to be discussed and cheap in terms of computational cost, the agent has been implemented following a mechanical-rational approach [67]. Consequently, albeit the default action for the animal is a diffusive random walk, thanks to which the agent is able to explore the environment without incurring in *lock-ins*, the same agent has been further upgraded. Indeed, it was given a complex architecture for reasoning and planning, according to the *Belief-Desire-Intention* idea (*BDI*). By doing so, the system is both realistic, easily interpretable and flexible.

Specifically, an agent is given typical big mammals behaviors, according to literature [82]: it wanders around while looking for resources (if it necessitates them), it arranges its movement schemes in order to reach said resources, it makes effort in avoiding stressful situations and areas (e.g. dangerous areas), unless it is unavoidable (e.g. because the animal has no resources anymore; it obviously follows a priority order). Moreover, the corridor is perceived as a neutral area: it is not considered as dangerous, nor as an incentive. Finally, communication among agents is not implemented (although further studies may like to model it using the FIPA protocol). The abstract design is shown in Fig. 4.2 (activity diagram).

For each simulation step, the agents behaves as described in the activity diagram. To begin with, it perceives its surrounding environment and its inner states (resources reservoirs in first place); then it can (i) keep on following its current plan, if not yet satisfied, (ii) select a new plan if the previous one was satisfied or if it not sound anymore with the inner belief, (iii) select a new *desire* if the previous plan was successfully satisfied (meaning the associated desire was fulfilled). Moreover, “instantaneous plan” can be also implemented: they will be executed at the same time, thus allowing more flexibility to the choice of desires and plans [62, 64].

One final remark: such kind of simulations not only allow interactions among individuals and the environment, but among different species too. For instance, one could be willing to study a prey-predator dynamics when green corridors are present; therefore, as we chose to simulate a single specie to begin with, we nonetheless called it *prey* as it refers to vegetarian mammals.

Once again, the implementation follows the design: to begin with, the agent *prey*’s attributes are defined (Fig. 4.3) as inner parameters, whose value is initially set arbitrarily; they are going to be better tuned during further

Fig. 4.2 Activity diagram.

development of the project. After that, the aforementioned hybrid architecture was coded with GAMA platform [63] “moving” *skills* and *simple_bdi* plugin. The main *BDI* methods are summarized in table (Tab. 4.1). In addition, in Appendix B (Model code) the complete code is listed; you would probably be interested in knowing that species *prey* implementation begins at line 75.

Fig. 4.3 Agent *prey*'s icon and typical parameters.

Table 4.1 Agent *prey*'s list of methods.

	Method	Description
Belief	has_resource	The agent knows that some resources are available
	target	The agent knows the targets (place or resource) position
	on_peril	The agents perceives a nearby area as dangerous
Desire	have_resource	The agent's goal is to get enough resources to live (top priority)
	avoid_peril	The agents second goal is to avoid dangerous or stressful situations (lower priority)
	wander	If it has not other desires to be fulfilled, the agent wanders.
Intention	get_resource	have_resource not satisfied: the agent tries to obtain the resource that it believe to be its target
	define_res_target	(subintention) have_resource not satisfied: if it does not have target resources, the agent looks for one
	choose_res_target	(subintention) have_resource not satisfied: if the animal finds many resources, it chooses one of them as target
	avoid_peril	have_resource satisfied: the animal avoids the dangerous area
	wander	(have_resource satisfied AND avoid_peril satisfied) OR (have_resource satisfied AND define_resource_target non satisfied): the agent explores the environment by wandering

4.2 Tools and Software

Since the simulation does not require high computational cost, it was possible to run them on a personal laptop (Intel Core 2 Duo T6500, 4 Gb RAM). A single simulation with graphic interface requires, on average, real time = 16s : 26 to reach t=1000 cycles).

The model was implemented on the advanced agent-based platform GAMA 1.8 [63]. As a useful feature, it allows the user to follow the system evolution in real time with a graphic interface, to inspect it and to obtain meaningful information for qualitative studies and validation. Finally, GAMA implements the BDI architecture as plug-in, thus making it accessible and easily manageable.

Data have been saved in CSV format and stored in personal devices. They are available under request.

Data analysis was performed in Python Jupyter Notebooks (Copyright ©2018 Project Jupyter, last update Apr 20, 2018, <http://jupyter.org/index.html>). Pandas, Scipy and Matplotlib libraries have been extensively used.

4.3 Quantitative variables and measurements

Exploring the whole parameter space is beyond the scopes of the present project. As mentioned above, environmental values have been chosen arbitrarily in order for them to be plausible, but without being adherent to real data, the reason being the toy model explanatory purpose (not predictive, though). Hence, from now on, the only meaningful varying parameter will be $width_{cor}$, namely the corridor width. In addition to it, the main quantitative variable the track to system dynamics is the total number of animals N (Fig. 4.4). Its evolution in time will be further analyzed. Moreover, to let the user discover other simulation features, he/she is allowed to look at the time evolution of two monitors showing, respectively, the animals reservoir distribution (if we say that a resource corresponds to food, it means that we are monitoring $res_supplies =$ inner energy) and the animals distribution within the environment (divided into starting, dangerous and arrival area) (Fig. 4.6).

Fig. 4.4 Evolution of animals number in time, as shown by GAMA graphic interface.

Fig. 4.5 Inner resources monitor; following the programming code (Appendix B), such monitors visualize the distribution of each animal reservoirs after dividing their possible values into three bins ($res_supplies = 0$, no reservoirs left, hence the animal needs to find resources and is prone to face perils; $res_supplies \in]0;20[$, the animal starts looking for resources; $res_supplies > 20$, the animal has plenty of resources and is satisfied).

Fig. 4.6 Animals distribution within the environment monitor (“left” means $x_{An} \in [0; 2/5 \text{ dim}]$, “middle” is $x_{An} \in]2/5 \text{ dim}; 3/5 \text{ dim}[$, “right” is $x_{An} \in [3/5 \text{ dim}; \text{dim}]$)

The reason why N was chosen as reference variable is twofold: on one hand, to show how to measure and analyze any desired quantitative variable within the simulation; on the other hand, to follow the literature suggestions concerning the the best measurements to evaluate the corridors effectiveness [35]. As shown in Fig. 4.7, number N (presence) and animals distribution (movement) are quite cheap in terms of research cost nor they require a cross-generation analysis, albeit being relevant for field research. Moreover, said variables are not only less costly then others when field studies are concerned, but they also require few computational power during simulations as they scale as $O(N)$.

Fig. 4.7 As stated in [35], among the numerous variables described in literature to address the corridors efficacy, presence and movement of animals are considered as meaningful while not being computationally costly nor time greedy (they do not need to be studied within many generations). Hence, they were considered to be particularly suitable for this preliminary analysis. In the graph, the circles dimension quantify of much each variable is considered relevant to conservation assessment, against cost of field studies and the needed time to complete the study.

4.4 An example

A single simulation is obtained by running the model and by letting the system dynamics to evolve according to coded behaviors. In principle, there is not a definite goal towards whom the system should evolve, not a final stable state exists; as a consequence, a time threshold $t_{stop} = 1000$ cycles was conventionally chosen in order to stop the simulation. However, as shown in Appendix A, said choice does not influence significantly the

subsequent quantitative analysis. Figure 4.8 and following ones show an example of system evolution, compared to the respective monitors. N time evolution will be further analyzed in the following section. Note that the example simulation is characterized by $width_{cor} = 20$. Other parameters are set as in Appendix B “Model code”.

In Fig. 4.8 we can see an initial setting where animals are scattered in a safe area. Once the simulation is run, agents pursue their main *desire*, namely to obtain resources while their own reservoirs deplete. It is possible that they randomly move on a corridor, which is not seen as a peril nor as an incentive (Fig. 4.9). After many agents exhaust their reservoirs, a first migration towards the second safe area can be detected (Fig. 4.10). Triggered by resource shortage, the animals are then able to modify their *avoid_peril* intention by changing priority to *define_resource_target*, so that they can satisfy their *get_resource_desire*: as a consequence, movements across the dangerous area that are not purely random happen, mainly by those animals that do not perceive the corridor (Fig. 4.11). The agents migration then lead to an overall balance between the two safe areas (phenomenon that is registered by the population distribution monitor) (Fig. 4.12). Finally, resources in both areas are totally consumed due to the migration of agents that are now equally distributed (Fig. 4.13).

Although it is preliminary, an animated simulation helps to observe the effect of corridors when they act as safe passage areas; at the same time, it is also possible to study what happens when migration is facilitated, that is, when animal populations are eased in moving towards areas that are rich in resources: when the number is too high with respect to the environmental recovery rates, the second safe area would probably be depleted, too. In order to gain a deeper insight into such scenarios, realistic parameters from real data should be implemented; a simulation predictive power is particularly handy when considering not only the population, but also the environmental resources management while they are affected by agent-environment interactions.

Finally, an example of this kind shows how to inquiry response variables in real time by looking at the temporal evolution of the most significant ones - as far as environmental conservation is concerned, of course - and by aggregating them in appropriate ways.

Fig. 4.8 $t=0$ cycle

Fig. 4.9 $t=30$ cycles

Fig. 4.10 $t=200$ cycles

Fig. 4.11 $t=500$ cycles

Fig. 4.12 $t=850$ cycles

Fig. 4.13 $t=t_{stop}=1000$ cycles

Fig. 4.14 Evolution of the number of animals N in time (referred to the example simulation presented in the subsection). Note that N is progressively decreasing due to several crossings of the dangerous area as in Fig. 4.11).

4.5 Quantitative analysis

For each experimental set (defined by the parameters choice), measuring the chosen control variables in time means studying the global system dynamics. In the following particular case, the total number of animals N is considered. In order for the results to be statistically relevant, repeated measurements are performed, so

that we can observe the mean evolution and its fluctuations ($\hat{N}(t) \pm \sigma_N(t)$). Note that, by using simulations as testbeds for repeated measurements guarantee a higher statistical relevance of the results. In Fig. 4.15 I show how to mediate over repeated simulations (for clarity reasons, only 10 of them are shown) in order to get ($\hat{N}(t) \pm \sigma_N(t)$). I recall that, given the total number of measurements M , we define:

$$\hat{N} = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{i=1}^M N_i \quad \sigma_N = \sqrt{\frac{1}{M-1} \sum_{i=1}^M (N_i - \hat{N})^2}$$

Fig. 4.15 Left: ten superimposed repeated measurements of N vs t . Right: mean behavior of $N(t)$, along with the associated standard deviation.

As stated above, $width_{cor}$ is the tested parameter within the present example. Hence, the experimental set includes simulations run with the following values:

$$width_{cor} = [0, 10, 20, 30, 40, 50, 60, 70, 80, 90, 100]$$

that is:

$$\frac{width_{cor}}{length_{cor}} = [0, 1/2, 1, 3/2, 2, 5/2, 3, 7/2, 4, 9/2, 5]$$

in this case, $dim = 100$ is the environment dimension.

A cumulative plot of all experimental sets is shown in Fig. 4.16. In particular, what evolves is the mean value of \hat{N} in time.

By looking at the data, one can investigate the dependence of the control variable N over the parameter $width_{cor}$. As a consequence, these results can be used to speculate about the effectiveness of corridors during environmental interventions. The simplest way to verify the functional dependence $N(width_{cor})$ requires a *scatter plot* \hat{N} vs $width_{cor}$, once a common temporal value is fixed³. In fact, by “freezing” the temporal evolution at a given time, one can compare the data over different experiments. $t = 1000$ is chosen as reference constant t value (justification of such choices can be traced back in Appendix A). A graph $\hat{N}(t = 1000)$ vs $width_{cor}$ is shown in Fig. 4.17. It is particularly interesting to note that, although fitting the data with a particular function is not allowed, since one can hardly make a prior hypothesis about its shape, a strong correlation is nonetheless spotted. As a first approximation, in fact, statistical tests of linear (Pearson) and monotone (Spearman) correlation give meaningful values: $\rho_{XY} = \frac{\sigma_{XY}}{\sigma_X \sigma_Y} = 0.97$. The associated p-value is $1.2 \cdot 10^{-6}$ (with $X = width_{cor}$ and $Y = \hat{N}(t = 1000)$). $r_{Spearman} = 0.98$.

³In Appendix A, I present a preliminary analytic study to assess the results of choosing a constant t value, compared to the global system dynamics.

Fig. 4.16 Different experiments defined by different values of $width_{cor}$. Each curve corresponds to $\hat{N}(t)$ (standard deviation is not shown for clarity reasons).

Fig. 4.17 $\hat{N}(t = 1000)$ vs $width_{cor}$ scatter plot; error bars represent the associated error $\sigma_{N(t=1000)}$. Note that, albeit determined in the usual statistical way, the error can hardly be considered a proper standard deviation since we can not assure that the global behavior would follow a gaussian distribution. Nonetheless, computing the error over repeated measurements quantify the uncertainty that comes from systematic studies.

From the point of view of an environmental architect, the graph is particularly relevant in the following sense: a clear inflection is present in the interval $30 \leq width_{cor} \leq 60$ (it is guaranteed by a constant fit $\hat{N}(t = 1000) = 24.10 \pm 0.04 \cdot width_{cor}$, $\chi^2_{red} = 0.02$). This suggests that, when the efficacy is gauged by considering how many animals the corridor safeguard, that of a $dim = 30$ corridor is compatible with that of a $dim = 60$; consequently, such information would allow to save resources and to design green corridors in a more efficient way. An *in silico* testbed could then be exploited in order to strengthen cost assessment procedures, in order to evaluate each possible configuration and to guide the choice of the most suitable one.

4.6 Discussion

In the present section, I introduced a simple agent-based toy model. It simulates the dynamics of a system evolving within an environment that is characterized by the presence of green corridors and resources. To begin with, said model was designed so that it could represent the principal characteristics of the studied system by relying on environmental biology knowledges and after performing due simplifications. By doing so, it was possible to reproduce *in silico* a dynamic environment in which proactive agents act. Finally, their dynamics is generated during a simulation *run* on top of individual behaviors. After that, the model was implemented in a suitable IT environment that was chosen because of its efficiency and flexibility. In particular, coding the model by means of a *BDI* architecture was particularly helpful when managing agents with a high level programming language, that is both adapt for dealing with complexity and interpretable; hence, future collaboration among modelers and researchers can be promoted. I expect further developing of the present project by exchanging knowledge and expertise, so that a complete and valid model could be obtained and successfully applied in real cases.

After design and implementation steps, it was suggested how to use the model. In order to do so, a toy model was proposed. To begin with, qualitative animations were considered to observe the overall development; after that, quantitative variables to gauge the evolution were defined and measured. Finally, by treating simulations as a reproducible experimental testbed, a statistical analysis was successfully performed on top of repeated experiments. Such a quantitative analysis helped us to identify dependencies and correlations among variables and parameters; as a case study, it was shown the trend of N vs $width_{cor}$. Looking at the resulting graph gave us the idea of a constant dependence interval that could suggest new ways to handle corridors dimensions while preserving animal populations and, at the same time, reducing their costs. Obviously, the case study can only be considered a paradigmatic example and not as a definitive result since the model is yet to be completely validated by looking at the population scales and by exploring the whole parameter space. However, I believe that such an example could provide a meaningful insight of the power of computational simulations. In fact, simulations allow researchers and policy makers to observe and predict phenomena that are intrinsically nonlinear and hence hardly tractable from a *a priori* analysis. On the contrary, such phenomena emerge from the complex interactions among agents and with the environment. Simulating them would hopefully shed new light while improving our understanding and interventions efficacy.

Conclusion

Safeguarding healthy ecosystems is a crucial challenge: not only it is of priority importance according to ethical views of the human-nature relationship, but it is also a must to maintain services and resources that are necessary for economy and society. Consequently, green corridors are of utmost relevance, hence they have been being studied, designed and realized as infrastructures to tackle fragmentation of territories and improve links among habitats. Numerous corridors can nowadays be found worldwide while, as we write, others are being built thanks to the efforts of researchers and governments. However, designing a green corridor is but a simple task: on one hand, scholars must properly assess and balance costs and benefits of such ambitious works; on the other, an effective cross-talk among researchers and local policy makers should be pursued. As a consequence, many mathematical models have been developed during the last decades, so that they could help field researches and works by developing new knowledge and, possibly, by anticipating systems evolution. Among different kinds of models, computational simulations offer the possibility to handle complex systems composed by discrete agents, with inner states that mimic typical animal behaviors, embedded in dynamic environments. In particular, for the present project the *Belief-Desire-Intention* architecture was applied to implement said inner states: in fact, it allows the researcher to program each individual *as if* it was capable of performing rational or committed choices. Moreover, thanks to the BDI being associated to high level, user friendly plugins, such choice would hopefully promote collaboration and usage even by those researchers that are not particularly proficient when dealing with artificial intelligence.

Then, an Agent-Based model was designed and implemented: its purpose was to address the case of green corridors being placed in a dynamical context by following a bottom-up approach; as a result, this model is consistent with shared and accepted knowledge about individual behaviors of a given species and is not grounded on top of abstract hypothesis about the entire system dynamics. In addition, complex behaviors emerge spontaneously from the interactions between agents and the environment. Hence, this model main purpose is to comprehend ecological and social dynamics that are typical of the considered ecosystem, as well as to assist field researches by providing a versatile testbed in which generating reliable and quantitative data and speculating about likely predictions. In fact, the model is particularly suitable for measuring and gauging meaningful quantities to evaluate a corridor effectiveness in an efficient and precise way. An example of quantitative analysis is also provided and it is suggested how to get useful results for biodiversity conservation even with narrower than expected, but well placed corridors. In addition, having qualitative animations could surely be of great help to interpret the data and the numerous field hypothesis. However, in the present model, parameters, variables and the geographical context were kept abstract, as realistic values were not applied. There were a few reasons for doing so: first of all, to show the robustness of the approach by letting the system evolve in a likely manner despite its parameters not being appropriately tuned; second, to provide a general and flexible framework that can eventually be specified in real scenarios and according to the users' needs; third, because the model validation and a first attempt to tailor in according to a specific area is the central argument

of the second half of the present project, namely Roberto Costantino's thesis at the Scuola di Studi Superiori di Torino "Ferdinando Rossi".

5.1 Going further

I believe that the novelty of the present project is represented by two key aspects: a new combination of modeling elements, and the explicit effort to make a simulation that could be accessible and understandable even for those researchers with little programming skills, so that an interdisciplinary collaboration could be promoted. Consequently, the project can be further developed in two main directions: an IT one, by implementing additional elements of complexity and new configurations from ecological knowledge (e.g. communication among individuals, learning and so on). Then, a second way is more related to nature studies, as the model can be tailored to address a specific territory and a particular species. Tuning the parameters appropriately will do so. According to this second case, spin-off of the original model will surely be more "rigid", which means being specifically oriented to study a specific ecosystem, but they will nonetheless be able to generate realistic data.

Finally, I would like to remark that simulations, easily interpretable thanks to their animations, can also be used for communication purposes: they can involve people and convey powerful ideas about the effects and the possible benefits of ecological corridors. In this sense, simulations can be used to assist decision making processes. Hopefully, the enhanced possibility to explore different configurations and to speculate about the outcomes using reliable tools may help researchers, workers and policy makers to best administrate many environments.

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Appendix A

To describe analytically the dynamics of the given system, it is possible to consider a simplified version of differential equation for malthusian growth/decrease. I consider the continuous case and I do not add stochastic variations for the decreasing rates (they would imply a Itô-like analysis). Hence, the simplest equation for said dynamics is:

$$\lim_{\Delta t \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta N}{\Delta t} = \frac{dN}{dt} = -p(\text{cross}) \cdot p(\text{in_dang_zone}) \cdot p(\text{die}) \cdot N \quad (\text{A.1})$$

The equation describes a constant decrease of animal numbers due to death occurring within the dangerous zone. As births are not initially considered, no growth terms are included. Eq A.1 can be rewritten as:

$$\frac{dN}{dt} = -P_1 \cdot P_2 \cdot P_3 \cdot N \quad (\text{A.2})$$

where the formal limit to infinitesimal time interval was applied. N is the mean number of animals (considered control variable; note that, for notation lightness, N corresponds to \hat{N} from now on). Stochastic phenomena are depicted by the following probability terms: $p(\text{cross}) = P_1$ represents the probability that an animal decides to leave the shelter zone in order to begin the crossing; $p(\text{in_dang_zone}) = P_2$ corresponds to the probability of crossing animal being in the dangerous zone; $p(\text{die}) = P_3$ is implemented as a model parameter, and corresponds to death chance. In particular, $P_3 = \text{cost}$ as it is a fixed model parameter and $P_2 = 1 - \frac{A_{\text{corridor}}}{A_{\text{peril}}} = \text{cost}$ for each simulation. P_2 contains the dependency of N on $\text{width}_{\text{cor}}$, since $A_{\text{corridor}} = \text{length}_{\text{cor}} \cdot \text{width}_{\text{cor}}$.

Equation A.2 is easily solvable if and only if one explicitly knows P_1 . For instance, P_1 could be independent from N , thus $N(t) = N_0 e^{-At}$ with $A = P_1 \cdot P_2 \cdot P_3$. The case $P_1 \propto N$ (even in non-linear or stochastic fashion) is obviously more difficult; in general, it is not possible to assume *a priori* any functional dependence, as an animal may leave (by design) the shelter zone because of non-deterministic movements or from resource depletion (which is itself dependent on the number of foraging animals). Hence, the most general form for eq. A.2 is:

$$\frac{dN(t; \text{width}_{\text{cor}})}{dt} = -P_1(N) \cdot P_2(\text{width}_{\text{cor}}) \cdot P_3 \cdot N \quad (\text{A.3})$$

with

$$\frac{\partial \text{width}_{\text{cor}}}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (\text{A.4})$$

since $\text{width}_{\text{cor}}$ is a fixed parameter for each simulation.

This way of reasoning leads to two important results (at least, as long as the present thesis is concerned):

1. Changing variables lead to:

$$t \cdot (P_2(\text{width}_{cor}) \cdot P_3) \rightarrow \tau; \quad (\text{A.5})$$

$$\frac{dN(\tau)}{d\tau} = -P_1(N) \cdot N \quad (\text{A.6})$$

being width_{cor} a multiplicative constant for the dynamics of a single simulation. If it exists and is analytically expressible, a solution is in the form:

$$N(\tau) = J(\tau) \quad (\text{A.7})$$

Therefore, to evaluate the dependence of N on the parameter width_{cor} over different simulations, it is possible to fix to constant any conventional value of t , so that $\tau = \text{width}_{cor} \cdot \text{const}$ and so $N(\tau) = N(\text{width}_{cor})$.

2. Generating the dynamics with Agent-Based simulations allows one to derive the posterior evolution of the given system; thus, it is possible to study its characteristics without having to know *a priori* the form of P_1 . By doing so, it is possible to observe phenomena and correlations that, in principle, one can not forecast by means of analytic studies as they emerge from interaction between agents and the environment within the given complex system.

Model code

Here the complete programming code is shown. It includes agent definitions as well as simulation and data visualization. As this is the basic “skeleton” which is useful for toy models, I would suggest to extend it in order to improve the consistence with real data and behaviors. If doing so, it is recommended to properly cite the original work.

The syntax is correct for GAMA 1.8 (<https://github.com/gama-platform/gama/releases>) in Gaml language (Java dialect).

Listing B.1 "Ecological Corridors" GAMA program

```
1 /**
2  * Name: corridors
3  * Author: Daniele Proverbio
4  * Description: Ecological corridors modeling
5  */
6
7 model corridors
8
9 global torus: torus_environment
10 {
11     //parameters
12     int number_of_preys <- 30 min:1 max:100; //number of vegetarian mammals
13     int dimension <- 100; //dimension of environment
14     int nb_perils <- 1; //how many dangerous areas
15     int nb_corridors <- 1; // how many corridors
16     int corridor_width <- 20; //corridor width (my variable)
17     float proba_die <- 0.01 min:0.0 max:1.0; //dieing probability in dangerous area
18     bool torus_environment <- false;
19
20     //-----
21     //experimentalist's measurements:
22     int nb_preys -> {length (prey)};
23     //-----
24     //initialise
25     init{
26         create prey number: number_of_preys {
27             location <- {rnd (2/5*dimension - 2) + 1, rnd (dimension - 2) + 1 };
28         }
29
30         create peril number:nb_perils {
31             self.shape <- rectangle(1/5*dimension, dimension);
```

```

    self.location <- { dimension/2, dimension/2};
31 }
    create corridor number:nb_corridors {
33     self.shape <- rectangle(1/5*dimension, corridor_width);
        self.location <- { dimension/2, dimension/2};
35     }
    create resource number:100 {
37     location <- {(rnd(4/5*dimension-2)+1+3/5*dimension)mod dimension, rnd(dimension-2)+1 };
        }
39 }

41 reflex stop_simulation when: (time > 1000){ //to stop simulation at given time
        do pause;
43     }
    reflex create_resource when:(time mod 200)=0){ //to create resources dynamically
45     create resource number:3;
        }
47 reflex save_data when: every(1#cycles){ //save the following text into the given text file.
        save [cycle,nb_preys] to: "../models/log/corridor10_20.csv" type:"csv" rewrite: false;
49     }
51 }

//Set agents and environment
53 //-----
//set grid of resources (for instance vegetation) [dynamical environment]
55 grid env width:dimension height:dimension neighbors:8 use_individual_shapes:false use_regular_agents:false
{rgb color <- #lightgreen ;} //other specifications may be added here
57 //-----
//species Peril (dangerous zone)
59 species peril{
    aspect default{draw shape color: #white;}
61 }
//-----
63 //species Corridor
species corridor{
65     int corridor_resources <- 100; //for example
        aspect default{draw shape color: #orange;}
67 }
//-----
69 //species Resource
species resource {
71     int food <- 100;
        aspect default{draw square(5) color: #green;}
73 }
//-----
75 //species Prey
species prey skills: [moving] control:simple_bdi{
77     float viewdist<-20.0;

```

```

79 float speed <- 2.0;
float maxRes <- 50.0;
float res_supplies <- 50.0 min: 0.0 max:maxRes; //inner reservoirs of resources
81 file my_icon <- file("../includes/data/deer.png");

83 reflex starve{res_supplies <- res_supplies - 1;}

85 reflex checkCell{
  list<peril> nearby_peril <- (peril overlapping (circle (0) ));
87 list<corridor> nearby_corridor <- (corridor overlapping (circle (0) ));
  if(length(nearby_peril)!=0 and length(nearby_corridor)=0){
89     if(flip(proba_die)){
          do die;
91     }
  }
93 }

95 geometry peril_perceived_area <- (cone(heading-60,heading+60) -->
--> intersection world.shape) intersection circle(1/2*viewdist); //field of view
97

//behaviors (verbatim, thanks to simple_bdi architecture)
99 predicate define_resource_target <- new_predicate("define_resource_target");
predicate get_resource <- new_predicate("get_resource");
101 predicate avoid_peril <- new_predicate("avoid_peril");
predicate wander <- new_predicate("wander");
103

//believes
105 predicate has_resource <- new_predicate("has_resource");
point target;
107

//to begin with, every animal wanders (intention)
109 init{do add_desire(wander);}

111 //if the agent perceive a resource in its perceived area and is starving, it adds a belief concening
//its location and remove its wandering intention
113 perceive target:resource in:viewdist {
  if(myself.res_supplies < 20){
115     focus id:"location_resource" var:location;
    ask myself {do remove_intention(wander, false);}
117   }
}

119

//if the agent perceive a nearby peril in its perceived area, it adds a belief concening its
121 //location and remove its wandering intention
perceive target:peril in:(peril_perceived_area) {
123   if(myself.res_supplies > 1){
    focus id:"location_peril" var:location;
125     ask myself {do remove_intention(wander, false);}
  }
}

```

```

    }
127 }

//if the agent has the belief that there are resources at given location, it adds the desire to get
//that resource
129 rule belief: new_predicate("location_resource") new_desire: get_resource strength:10.0;

131

//if the agent has the belief that there are perils at given location, it adds the desire to avoid them
133 rule belief: new_predicate("location_peril") new_desire: avoid_peril strength:8.0;

135

//PLANS
137 // plan that has for goal to fulfill the wander desire
plan letsWander intention:wander {do wander;}

139

//plan that has for goal to fulfill the get_resource desire
141 plan getResource intention:get_resource {
    //if the agent does not have chosen a target location, it adds the sub-intention to define a
143 //target and puts its current intention on hold
    if (target = nil) {
145         do add_subintention(get_resource,define_resource_target, true);
147         do current_intention_on_hold();
    } else {
149         do goto target: target ;
        //if the agent reach its location, it updates it takes the resource, updates its belief base,
        //and remove its intention to get resource
151         if (target = location) {
            resource current_resource <- resource first_with (target = each.location);
153             if current_resource != nil{
                //do add_belief(has_resource);
155                 self.res_supplies <- self.res_supplies + 10;
                current_resource.food <- current_resource.food - 10;
157                 if(current_resource.food = 0){ask current_resource {do die;}}
            }
159         }
        do remove_belief(new_predicate("location_resource", -->
161         --> ["location_value":target]));
        target <- nil;
163         do remove_intention(get_resource, true);
    }
165 }
}

167

//plan that has for goal to fulfill the define resource target desire. This plan is instantaneous
//(does not take a complete simulation step to apply).
169 plan choose_source_target intention: define_resource_target instantaneous: true{
171     list<point> possible_resource <- get_beliefs(new_predicate("location_resource")) -->
    --> collect (point(get_predicate(mental_state (each)).values["location_value"]));
173     if (empty(possible_resource)) {

```

```

175         do remove_intention(get_resource, true);
        } else {
177             target <- (possible_resource with_min_of (each distance_to self)).location;
        }
179         do remove_intention(define_resource_target, true);
    }

181 //plan that has for goal to fulfill the avoid_peril desire
plan avoidPeril intention:avoid_peril {
183     self.heading <- 180 + self.heading;
    do remove_belief(new_predicate("avoid_peril", ["location_value"::target]));
185     target <- nil;
    do remove_intention(avoid_peril, true);
187 }

189 //aspect species prey
aspect default { draw circle(0.5) color: #red;}
191 aspect info {
    draw circle(0.5) color: #red ;
193     draw string(res_supplies with_precision 2) size: 3 color: #black ;
    }
195 aspect icon {draw my_icon size: 3.5 ;}
}

197 //-----
199 //Definition of the experiment
experiment Ecological_corridor type: gui{
201     parameter 'Number_of_preys' var: number_of_preys;
    parameter 'Corridor_width' var: corridor_width;
203     parameter 'Probability_of_accidental_death' var: proba_die;

205     output{
        display grille{
207             grid env;
            species resource;
209             species peril;
            species corridor;
211             species prey aspect:icon;
        }
213 //display info_display { //inspects env and species directly
            // grid env;
215             // species resource;
            // species prey aspect: info;
217             //}

        display Population_information{
219             chart "Number_animals" type: series background: rgb("white") -->
            --> axes: rgb("black") position: {0,0} size: {1.0,0.5}{
221                 data "Number_animals" color: rgb("blue") value: nb_preys style: spline ;
            }
        }
    }
}

```

```
223     }
224     chart "Prey_Resources_Distribution" type: histogram -->
225     --> background: #white size: {0.5,0.5} position: {0, 0.5} { //monitor
226     data "]0]" value: prey count (each.res_supplies <= 0.0) color:#blue;
227     data "]0;20[" value: prey count ((each.res_supplies > 0.0) and (each.res_supplies -->
228     --> < 20.0)) color:#blue;
229     data "[20;50]" value: prey count ((each.res_supplies >= 20.0) and (each.res_supplies -->
230     --> <= 50.0)) color:#blue;
231     }
232     chart "Prey_Distribution" type: histogram -->
233     --> background: #white size: {0.5,0.5} position: {0.5, 0.5} { //monitor
234     data "left" value: prey count (each.location.x < 2/5*dimension) color:#red;
235     data "middle" value: prey count (each.location.x >= 2/5*dimension and each.location.x -->
236     --> <= 3/5*dimension) color:#red;
237     data "right" value: prey count ((each.location.x > 3/5*dimension)) color:#red;
238     }
239     }
240 }
```